

Siriono

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Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

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Entry tags: South American Religions, Religion

The Siriono are a seminomadic indigenous people who occupy an area of about 200 square miles in Northeastern Bolivia (Holmberg, 1960:4). This entry focuses on the Siriono living in the vicinity of the Rio Blanco around the time of 1942. At this time, the Siriono had very limited contact with outsiders. The Siriono lived in seminomadic bands led by chiefs. The position of chief was held on the basis of prestige, and was more about social status than actual authority. The Siriono did not have an official political leadership position, and the nuclear family was the main social and economic unity. The Siriono religion was minimally developed, and did not play a large role in the daily lives of individuals. There was no complex religious system, no shamans or priests, and no extensive mythology or folklore. Rather, the religion consisted of taboos, ceremonies, and the belief in spirits and the moon as the creator deity.

Date Range: 1917 CE - 1943 CE

Region: Vicinity of the Rio Blanco

Region tags: South America, Bolivia (Plurinational State of)

Vicinity of the Rio Blanco, ca. 1942

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sf21-001>

– Source 1 Description: Holmberg, A. R. (1950). *Nomads Of The Long Bow: The Siriono Of Eastern Bolivia*. Smithsonian Institution. Institute Of Social Anthropology. Washington: U.S. Govt. Print. Off.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "Our previous knowledge of the Siriono, which is very scanty, dates from 1693, when they were first seen for a few days by Father Cyprian Barrac. At that time the Siriono were occupying the deep forests in the southern part of the same region which they inhabit today. After first contact, and before their expulsion in 1767, the Jesuits probably made several attempts to missionize them. At any rate, in 1765 a few Siriono were coaxed into the mission of Buena Vista and were later transferred to the mission of Santa Rosa on the Rio Guaporé. So far as we know, no other attempt was made to missionize them until comparatively recent times. Of these endeavors most have failed, not so much because of warlikeness, since this character has been falsely attributed to the Siriono, but because of their sensitivity to maltreatment and their adherence to nomadic life" (Holmberg, 1950:9[2]).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (Resolved Rating), indicates that internal warfare seems to be absent or rare (original code 1). Additionally, SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, indicates that the Siriono were not pacified for all or part of the twenty-five-year time period. Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (Resolved Rating), indicates that external warfare seems to be absent or rare (original code 1). Additionally, SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, indicates that the Siriono were not pacified for all or part of the twenty-five-year time period. Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: The Siriono do not have a complex religious system. Rather, they are united through the shared belief in supernatural beings, taboos, and ceremonial activities. Consequently, there is not a concept of assigning religious affiliation.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: The Siriono do not have a complex religious system. Rather, they are united through the shared belief in supernatural beings, taboos, and ceremonial activities. Consequently, there is not a concept or need for the recruitment of new members.

Does the religion have official political support

Answer 'yes' also in cases where the religious and political spheres are not distinguished from one another, but the religious group's activities are tied up with, and supported by, the functioning of the society at large.

– No

Notes: The Siriono do not have an official political leadership office or legal system, and the religious

system is limited. (see Holmberg, 1950: 49-60, 90).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for a conception of apostasy among the Siriono.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 2000

Notes: "...the total population of the Siriono today is probably about two thousand" (Holmberg, 1950: 9[5]).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: "Beyond the stratifications of sex and age, Siriono society is little differentiated as to status. A form of chieftainship does exist, but the prerogatives of this office are few. Such status divisions as castes, social classes, and specialized occupations are quite unknown" (Holmberg, 1950:58). "Shamans and medical practitioners are entirely lacking in this society..." (Holmberg, 1950:86[6]).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of scripture among the Siriono.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: No religious buildings are present among the Siriono. "The average house sheltering a band of from 60 to 80 people is approximately 60 feet long, 25 feet wide, 15 feet high at the center, and about 5 feet high at the frame. It can be constructed in about an hour's time. Seldom is more than 15 minutes or a half an hour spent in the construction of a lean-to for the night. Other types of buildings, such as cook houses, granaries, and club houses, are not built. A Siriono settlement consists of but a single hut, constructed in the manner described above" (Holmberg, 1950:18).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: No religious buildings are present among the Siriono. "The average house sheltering a band of from 60 to 80 people is approximately 60 feet long, 25 feet wide, 15 feet high at the center, and about 5 feet high at the frame. It can be constructed in about an hour's time. Seldom is more than 15 minutes or a half an hour spent in the construction of a lean-to for the night. Other types of buildings, such as cook houses, granaries, and club houses, are not built. A Siriono settlement consists of but a single hut, constructed in the manner described above" (Holmberg, 1950:18).

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of specific sacred sites.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "Upon inquiring of informants as to the fate of their souls after death, I was almost always given the answer that they did not know. There seemed, however, to be general agreement that the soul of the deceased may become an abačikwaia (evil spirit) or a kurúkwa (monster), but this form of survival informants were reluctant to contemplate for their own souls" (Holmberg, 1950:92).

Belief in afterlife:

– No

Notes: "...I, too, found no evidence to corroborate such a belief in a hereafter. While notions of an afterlife have crept in where the Indians have had contacts with the whites, these are clearly assignable to Christian influence" (Holmberg, 1950:91-92).

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a belief in reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "The corpse, extended with arms to the side, is wrapped in two mats of motacú palm and placed on a platform in the house. It is not oriented in any special way. With the deceased are placed his calabashes filled with water, his pipes, and fire. No food is left. Once the corpse is disposed of the house is abandoned; but before leaving, the men shoot arrows in all directions through the house to drive out the evil spirits. The band then moves on to a new location—often several days' journey away" (Holmberg, 1950:87[8]).

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cremation.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– No

Notes: "Aboriginally the Siriono do not bury their dead" (Holmberg, 1950:87[8]).

– Yes

Notes: "While living with the Siriono, I never had an opportunity to observe a funeral under strictly aboriginal conditions. However, I was present at a number of deaths at Tibaera where, according to informants, the mortuary rites were essentially the same as those which take place in the forest, except that the corpse was interred and that the house was not abandoned" (Holmberg, 1950:88[2]).

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of exposing corpses to elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: "The disposal of the corpse does not end contact with the dead. After the flesh has rotted, relatives of the deceased are obliged to return and bury the bones. If they are not buried, the soul of the deceased may return as an abačikwaia (evil spirit) or a kurúkwa (monster) and cause illness and death to the surviving members of the family" (Holmberg, 1950:89[2]).

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: Placed on platform in house and abandoned

Notes: "The corpse, extended with arms to the side, is wrapped in two mats of motacú palm and placed on a platform in the house. It is not oriented in any special way. With the deceased are placed his calabashes filled with water, his pipes, and fire. No food is left. Once the corpse is disposed of the house is abandoned; but before leaving, the men shoot arrows in all directions through the house to drive out the evil spirits. The band then moves on to a new location—often several days' journey away" (Holmberg, 1950:87[8]).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of co-sacrifices.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "With the deceased are placed his calabashes filled with water, his pipes, and fire" (Holmberg, 1950:87[8]).

↳ Personal effects:

– No

Notes: (Holmberg, 1950:87[8])

↳ Valuable items:

– No

Notes: (Holmberg, 1950:87[8])

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: "Aboriginally the Siriono do not bury their dead. The corpse, extended with arms to the side, is wrapped in two mats of motacú palm and placed on a platform in the house. It is not oriented in any special way. With the deceased are placed his calabashes filled with water, his pipes, and fire. No food is left. Once the corpse is disposed of the house is abandoned; but before leaving, the men shoot arrows in all directions through the house to drive out the evil spirits. The band then moves on to a new location—often several days' journey away" (Holmberg, 1950:87[8]). "The disposal of the corpse does not end contact with the dead. After the flesh has rotted, relatives of the deceased are obliged to

return and bury the bones. If they are not buried, the soul of the deceased may return as an abačikwaia (evil spirit) or a kurúkwa (monster) and cause illness and death to the surviving members of the family" (Holmberg, 1950:89[2]).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "...there is no belief in a hierarchy of gods who control the destiny of man. Yási (Moon) is the only supernatural being which the Siriono believe in" (Holmberg, 1950:90[2]).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: "...there is no belief in a hierarchy of gods who control the destiny of man. Yási (Moon) is the only supernatural being which the Siriono believe in...mythology imparts considerable power to this culture hero who was responsible for the creation of the world and all that is in it, and attesting to the fact that the moon still plays some role in the affairs of men are such beliefs as that the moon causes thunder and lightning by hurling peccaries and jaguars down to earth and that to sleep under the rays of the moon causes blindness. But the moon can scarcely be regarded as a supernatural being in the usual religious sense. It exerts little or no influence on the affairs of men, and no cult has grown up around it" (Holmberg, 1950:90[2]).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god, Yási, is a sky deity in the sense that it is the moon and resides in the sky.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Siriono.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Siriono.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: "But the moon can scarcely be regarded as a supernatural being in the usual religious sense. It exerts little or no influence on the affairs of men, and no cult has grown up around it" (Holmberg, 1950:90[2]).

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

"Indirect causal efficacy" refers to not being seen as consciously, directly and actively intervening in the human world, but their overall well being or general attitude has effects on, e.g., quality of harvest, success in war, health, etc.

– No

Notes: "But the moon can scarcely be regarded as a supernatural being in the usual religious sense. It exerts little or no influence on the affairs of men, and no cult has grown up around it" (Holmberg, 1950:90[2]).

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– No

Notes: "But the moon can scarcely be regarded as a supernatural being in the usual religious sense. It exerts little or no influence on the affairs of men, and no cult has grown up around it" (Holmberg, 1950:90[2]).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Upon inquiring of informants as to the fate of their souls after death, I was almost always given the answer that they did not know. There seemed, however, to be general agreement that the soul of the deceased may become an abačikwaia (evil spirit) or a kurúkwa (monster), but this form of survival informants were reluctant to contemplate for their own souls. Out of the confusion of ideas (or lack of them) that exist on the subject, it vaguely appears that the soul of a 'good' man, i.e., one who has abided by tribal custom and has the respect of his countrymen, does not return in the form of an evil spirit or monster to harass his surviving relatives, but that that of a 'bad' man, i.e., one who breaks tribal taboos and is disliked by his countrymen, may return in one of these forms to cause sickness and death to the living. That the souls of some of the dead can be relied upon to assist the living is clearly indicated by

the aforementioned practice of employing the skulls of some ancestors to cure disease. Informants, however, were never able to supply me with any clear-cut ideas as to what happens to the soul of a 'good' person after death. One thing seems clear as regards eschatological belief: there is no afterworld to which the soul departs" (Holmberg, 1950:92).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

"Indirect causal efficacy" refers to not being seen as consciously, directly and actively intervening in the human world, but their overall well being or general attitude has effects on, e.g., quality of harvest, success in war, health, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "Out of the confusion of ideas (or lack of them) that exist on the subject [of what happens to human souls after death], it vaguely appears that the soul of a 'good' man, i.e., one who has abided by tribal custom and has the respect of his countrymen, does not return in the form of an evil spirit or monster to harass his surviving relatives, but that that of a 'bad' man, i.e., one who breaks tribal taboos and is disliked by his countrymen, may return in one of these forms to cause sickness and death to the living" (Holmberg, 1950:92).

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The core of Siriono religious belief is centered in the fear of animistic spirits. The universe is thought to be peopled with detached evil spirits called abačikwaia, which are responsible for most of the misfortunes that befall the human race. Thus cold south winds, accidents, illnesses, bad luck, deaths, etc., are ascribed to the intervention of abačikwaia" (Holmberg, 1950:90[3]).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "The Siriono also believe in monsters, of whom they have great fear. These are called kurúkwa. Unlike the abačikwaia, which are invisible and formless, the kurúkwa are visible and somewhat resemble human beings. But they are large, ugly, black, and hairy" (Holmberg, 1950:90[4]).

– No

Notes: "These spirits [abačikwaia] are invisible and formless..." (Holmberg, 1950:90[3]).

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: "Knowledge of disease and medicine is not extensive. While a theory of natural causation is recognized with respect to such minor ailments as wounds, burns, and stomach trouble, the majority of maladies, as well as accidents, are thought to be caused by evil spirits called abačikwaia. These spirits enter the mouth or nose when a person is sleeping (especially when he is snoring) and settle in the regions where the pain is felt" (Holmberg, 1950:86).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Knowledge of disease and medicine is not extensive. While a theory of natural causation is recognized with respect to such minor ailments as wounds, burns, and stomach trouble, the majority of maladies, as well as accidents, are thought to be caused by evil spirits called abačikwaia. These spirits enter the mouth or nose when a person is sleeping (especially when he is snoring) and settle in the regions where the pain is felt" (Holmberg, 1950:86).

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "The violation of taboos, too, especially food taboos, may be regarded as one of the principal causes of disease. The conditions following a breach of tribal custom are particularly favorable for the entrance into the body of the innumerable evil spirits which are ever present in nature" (Holmberg,

1950:86[3]).

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

"Indirect causal efficacy" refers to not being seen as consciously, directly and actively intervening in the human world, but their overall well being or general attitude has effects on, e.g., quality of harvest, success in war, health, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "Thus cold south winds, accidents, illnesses, bad luck, deaths, etc., are ascribed to the intervention of abačikwaia" (Holmberg, 1950:90[3]).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "...there is no belief in a hierarchy of gods who control the destiny of man. Yási (Moon) is the only supernatural being which the Siriono believe in" (Holmberg, 1950:90[2]). However, in addition to Yási, abačikwaia (evil spirit), and kurúkwa (monster) are present among the Siriono (Holmberg, 1950:92).

Supernatural Monitoring

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "The violation of taboos, too, especially food taboos, may be regarded as one of the principal causes of disease. The conditions following a breach of tribal custom are particularly favorable for the entrance into the body of the innumerable evil spirits which are ever present in nature" (Holmberg, 1950:86[3]).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "The violation of taboos, too, especially food taboos, may be regarded as one of the principal causes of disease. The conditions following a breach of tribal custom are particularly favorable for the entrance into the body of the innumerable evil spirits which are ever present in nature" (Holmberg, 1950:86[3]).

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: "The absence of rigidity in standards of morality makes for relatively few offenses in the realm of sex. Such crimes as incest and rape are rare. When they do occur, they are believed to be followed by an automatic supernatural sanction; the offender becomes sick or dies" (Holmberg, 1950:61[2]).

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: "The violation of taboos, too, especially food taboos, may be regarded as one of the principal causes of disease. The conditions following a breach of tribal custom are particularly favorable for the entrance into the body of the innumerable evil spirits which are ever present in nature" (Holmberg, 1950:86[3]).

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: "The violation of taboos, too, especially food taboos, may be regarded as one of the principal causes of disease. The conditions following a breach of tribal custom are particularly favorable for the entrance into the body of the innumerable evil spirits which are ever present in nature" (Holmberg, 1950:86[3]).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: There is no concept of an afterlife among the Siriono.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: The only examples of supernatural punishment take the form of sickness and illness (See Holmberg, 1950: 61[2], 86[3]).

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: The only examples of supernatural punishment take the form of sickness and illness (See Holmberg, 1950: 61[2], 86[3]).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence or examples of supernatural beings bestowing rewards.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of an eschatology.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of castration.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: "While ceremonial life is almost negligible among the Siriono, membership in full adulthood is signified by participation in a bloodletting ceremony and drinking feast which is called hidai-idákwa. This is about the only ceremony performed by the Siriono" (Holmberg, 1950:83[6]).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: Some ceremonies are present, but participation does not appear to be mandatory.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

This question refers to the wider society in which the religious group is located.

– A band

Notes: The Siriono have no political authority beyond the local community, which is reflective of autonomous bands and villages (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: "...the system of education among the Siriono may best be characterized as informal, random, and haphazard" (Holmberg, 1950:77[2]).

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The same may be said [MPK: i.e., lack of success] for the Bolivian Government Indian School established at Casarabe—40 miles east of Trinidad—in 1937. However noble in its purpose, the function of this school ultimately resulted in the personal exploitation of the Indians by the staff, so that, through maltreatment, disease, and death, the number of Siriono was reduced from more than 300 in 1940 to less than 150 in 1945" (Holmberg, 1950:9[3]).

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– I don't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: The Siriono have no political authority beyond the local community, which is reflective of autonomous bands and villages (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: "The supply of food is rarely abundant and always insecure. Game is not plentiful; the techniques of hunting, fishing, and agriculture are very limited; patterns of food storage do not exist. Consequently, eating habits depend largely upon quantities of food available for consumption at the moment" (Holmberg, 1950:30[5]).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: "Although rivers and lakes abound in the territory traversed by the Siriono, all movement and transportation take place on foot, overland...The trails (ñénda) over which transportation and hunting take place are not built; they simply grow up from use" (Holmberg, 1950:42).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: "Within this society, the formal agencies of social control are almost entirely lacking. No such thing as a police force exists, and, as we have already seen, chieftainship, although theoretically an office of some power and distinction, is actually relatively unimportant as a means of controlling behavior" (Holmberg, 1950:60[4]).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: "Justice is an informal and private matter. Grievances are settled between the individuals involved, or among the members of the family in which they occur" (Holmberg, 1950:61[4]).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: "So intense is the individualism of the Siriono and so elastic the legal system, that crime and punishment are rare" (Holmberg, 1950:60-61).

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: "The best evidence we have for the relatively unwarlike character of the Siriono comes from the culture itself. Here are not found the organization, the numbers, or the weapons with which to wage war, aggressive or defensive. Moreover, war does not seem to be glorified in any way by the culture. The child is not educated in the art of war, nor is there a warrior class among the adults" (Holmberg, 1950:63[2]).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: "No records of time are kept, and no type of calendar exists. The year, with its division into months or 'moons,' is quite unknown" (Holmberg, 1950:48[2]).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: "In contrast to most other aboriginal peoples of the area in which they live, the Siriono are seminomadic forest dwellers who live more by hunting, fishing, and gathering than they do by farming" (Holmberg, 1950:21-22). The Siriono are primarily hunter-gatherers, with fishing as a supplemental source of subsistence. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

Notes: "In contrast to most other aboriginal peoples of the area in which they live, the Siriono are seminomadic forest dwellers who live more by hunting, fishing, and gathering than they do by farming" (Holmberg, 1950:21-22). The Siriono are primarily hunter-gatherers, with fishing as a supplemental source of subsistence. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.